

EFFECT OF ARAMID FIBER CLOTH ON CARBON/ARAMID FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

Hisaki Matsuda¹, Bing Xiao¹, Isamu Ohsawa¹, and Jun Takahashi¹

¹Department of Systems Innovation, the University of Tokyo.

E-mail: matsuda-hisaki@cfrtp.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp Submission identifier: ICCM22-I/617

Introduction and Preparation

Introduction

Carbon-fiber reinforced thermosetting plastics (CFRTP)

- ✓ Outstanding mechanical performance with lightweight
- ✓ Suited to complex shape part molding
- ✓ Easy to repair or recycle

→ Recycled CFRTP would increase in the market

- ✓ Instantaneous failure and lack of toughness

→ Optimizing the design of the hybrid with aramid

Figure 2: Hybrid effect of carbon/aramid [4]

Optimizing the design of hybrid with carbon/aramid hybrid and comparing with carbon/glass hybrid

[1] https://www.bmw.co.jp/ia/hill-models/bmw-ic32017/design.html [2] https://planetgreenrecycle.com/fundraising/recycle-the-beauty-of-scraps-materials [3] https://www.compositesworld.com/blog/post/building-confidence-in-recycled-carbon-fiber [4] T. Nishizu, On the improvement of mechanical properties of composite by hybrid composition, Proceeding of the 8th Int Reinforced Plastics Conference, 1982, pp. 149-152

Figure 1: CFRP recycling process [1-3]

Hybrid effect is the failure strain enhancement of the low elongation fibers in a hybrid composite and one of the methods to improve the toughness.

Aramid

- ✓ light weight and outstanding toughness
- ✓ keeping their performance through the recycling process

Preparation

Figure 3: Materials and manufacturing the hybrid

CPT Discontinuous CFRTP made from the recycled carbon fiber and PA6 Aramid Two continuous fiber cloth with different bundle thickness were used

	Name	Materials	Stacking sequence
Pure	CPT	CPT	C ₂₄
	Pure M0200s	CPT, M0200s	A ₁₆
	Pure M1000s	CPT, M1000s	A ₈
	Pure glass	CPT, Glass	G ₇
Hybrid	Hybrid M0200s	M0200s	[C ₈ /A ₄ /C ₄]s
	Hybrid M1000s	M1000s	[C ₈ /A ₂ /C ₄]s
	Hybrid glass	Glass	[C ₈ /G ₂ /C ₄]s

Table 1: The information of stacking sequences

Figure 4: M0200s and M1000s

Figure 5: The molding condition

Experimental

Test type	Dimension of specimen			Stroke speed	Number of specimen	Reference standard
	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)			
Tensile test	200	20	1.7	1mm/min	5	ASTM D3039
Three-point bending test	80	15	3.5	1mm/min	6	ASTM D790 03
Three-point impact test	80	15	3.5	3.8m/sec	6	JIS K 7084
Izod impact test	52	12	3.5	1.5m/sec	8	JIS K 7110

Table 2: The condition of each test

Three-point bending test

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2}$$

$$\epsilon_b = \frac{6\delta h}{L^2}$$

$$E_b = \frac{L^3}{4bh^3} \left(\frac{P}{\delta} \right)$$

where, σ_b : Flexural stress, P: Flexural load, L: Span between to supporters, b: the width of specimen, h: the thickness of specimen, ϵ_b : Flexure strain, δ : the deflection, E_b : Flexural modulus

Tensile test

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{bh}$$

$$\epsilon_t = \frac{\Delta l}{l}$$

$$E_t = \Delta\sigma_t / \Delta\epsilon_t$$

where, σ_t : Tensile stress, P: Tensile load, b: the width of specimen, h: the thickness of specimen, ϵ_t : Tensile strain, l: the length of specimen

Impact test

$$a = \frac{W}{hb}$$

where, a: Energy absorption, h: Thickness of specimen, b: Width of specimen

Figure 6: Three-point bending test

Results

Static test

Figure 7: The mechanical properties in three-point bending test and tensile test

Impact test

Figure 8: The mechanical properties in three-point impact test and Izod impact test

The hybrids showed ductile behavior with several load drops after the first peak and outstanding energy absorption abilities

Discussion and Conclusion

- ✓ Carbon/aramid improved the toughness of CPT successfully
- ✓ Thick bundles would show better stress transfer and load sustainability after the tension failure takes place first with the bottom carbon fiber layer breaking
- ✓ The middle layer with ductile fiber sustained the impacts after the bottom carbon layer broke in two impact tests.

Figure 9: The mechanical performances of the hybrid composites

Conclusion

- (1) In tensile test, the ductile fiber layer didn't bring its advantage in hybrid where the hybrids and CPT show similar performance
- (2) In the flexural and the dynamic tests, the hybrids with the aramid fiber can improve the toughness of CPT, which is expected to broaden the CFRTP application
- (3) The hybrid effect is more obvious in impact loads than the static loads
- (4) In this study, the hybrid with thick fiber bundles showed better performance and the bundle thickness can be an important parameter to control the mechanical performance
- (5) Both two hybrids with aramid cloth show superior to the one with glass cloth, which indicates the aramid cloth can have more potential to be applied to CFRTP hybrid
- (6) To maximize the reinforcement effect, further research about the lamination sequence and thickness of each layer should be carried out

Acknowledgements

Part of this study has been conducted as the Japanese METI project "the Future Pioneering Projects / Innovative Structural Materials Project" since 2013fy. The authors would like to express sincere appreciation to the project members who have provided valuable information and useful discussion.

1. Raising the position of the curve after the first peak
2. Increasing the modulus after the load drop
3. Keeping the curve at a high position and extend the final destruction period

Figure 10: The ideal load-displacement curve of the hybrid